

INFORMED CONSENT

Onboarding in SPLs: Challenges and Strategies

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I, Mr./Ms., with ID,
declare that I have been informed about the study "*Onboarding in SPLs: Challenges and Strategies*".

I declare that I have been informed of the objectives of the study and the type of interview in which I will participate. I also declare that my participation is voluntary and that my data will be treated anonymously.

I am also aware that I may at any time revoke my consent for my data to be used in the study, as well as my right of access, rectification, cancellation and opposition with respect to them. I have been informed that I have the right to know the results, as well as the way in which I can exercise all the above rights.

In view of the above, **I hereby give my authorization to participate in the collection of data** that may fulfill the objectives of the project, under the conditions detailed in the information sheet.

Place and Date:

Participant's signature: